

FINAL PROJECT REPORT

Analysis of Blockchain technology adoption factors: consumer perceptions, public initiatives, sectoral utilities and economic-regulatory barriers.

Call for proposals:

Plan Propio UGR - Proyectos precompetitivos (Jóvenes Doctores) **PPJIA2024-61**.

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1. Executive summary and rationale of the project

This project was designed to analyse the factors that condition the adoption of blockchain technology from a multidimensional perspective. In particular, it addressed the gap between the high technological potential of this technology and its effective adoption by consumers, organisations, and public administrations.

The scientific literature has pointed out that blockchain offers relevant benefits associated with the traceability of transactions, transparency of information systems, automation through smart contracts, and reduction of intermediaries. However, a number of factors have also been identified as limiting its expansion, including perceived complexity, lack of trust in platforms, regulatory uncertainty, implementation costs, and doubts about the economic sustainability of certain business models.

In order to address these issues, the project adopted an analytical approach that integrated three complementary dimensions. Firstly, the psychological-behavioural dimension linked to users' perceptions and attitudes towards technology has been analysed. Secondly, the sectoral and strategic dimension related to the application of blockchain in specific economic sectors has been examined. Finally, the economic-regulatory dimension has been considered, focusing on the identification of institutional and fiscal barriers that condition the implementation of this technology.

Despite being a pre-competitive project with a reduced final budget, the research has been oriented towards maximising the scientific return through a strategy based on a rigorous review of the literature, the development of empirical contrasts and the generation of results that can be published in international scientific journals.

2. Project objectives and degree of achievement

2.1 Objectives set out in the initial report

The project's initial report structured the research around three main lines of work. Firstly, it set out to analyse consumer perceptions and the role of public and sectoral initiatives in the adoption of blockchain. Secondly, it has been proposed to investigate the practical applications of the technology in different economic sectors, with a particular focus on tourism. Finally, it has been set as an objective to examine the economic, regulatory and tax barriers that may limit the adoption of this technology.

2.2 Assessment of the degree of compliance

The development of the project has made it possible to achieve a high degree of compliance with the objectives initially set.

The objectives related to the analysis of user perceptions and the identification of sectoral applications have been fully met through empirical studies, scientific publications and participation in international academic dissemination activities.

For its part, the objective relating to economic-regulatory analysis has been addressed in an exploratory manner, consistent with the pre-competitive nature of the project. In this sense, various economic and regulatory barriers that condition the adoption of blockchain have been identified and systematised, although the development of a fully structured legal-tax model has been proposed as a future line of research.

3. Project methodology

3.1 Literature review

During the development of the project, a rigorous review of the international scientific literature on blockchain adoption has been carried out. This review was carried out using a combination of methodological approaches including systematic reviews, bibliometric analyses and structured reviews aimed at developing conceptual frameworks.

The outcome of this process has identified the main theoretical determinants of the adoption of blockchain technologies and established a solid basis for the subsequent development of empirical analyses.

Beyond forming the theoretical basis of the project, the literature review has led to the publication of a scientific article entitled "Managing Emerging Risks and Sustainability in Blockchain Adoption for Tourism Operations", published in the journal *Information Technology & Tourism*, which is indexed in the Web of Science in the first quartile of its category.

3.2 Theoretical design and analytical models

From the literature review, integrative conceptual frameworks have been developed based on models of technology adoption widely used in academic research.

In particular, the project has incorporated elements from classical models of technology adoption and used the **Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R)** approach to analyse how certain environmental stimuli influence users' cognitive and attitudinal processes and, ultimately, their intention to use technology.

Relevant contextual variables, such as perceived security, data privacy and institutional support, have also been considered in order to explain the mechanisms that facilitate or hinder blockchain adoption.

Based on the proposed theoretical model, an empirical assessment has been carried out. At the time of writing this justification report, two research articles are in the review phase: (1) *From Stimuli to Adoption: An S-O-R Approach to Blockchain Use in Tourism*, which is in the third phase of review in the *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, indexed in Web of Science and ranked in the first quartile of its category; and (2) *Beyond the Hype: Mapping Blockchain Adoption Profiles in Tourism Using CHAID*, which is in the first phase of review in the *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, also indexed in Web of Science and ranked in the first quartile of its category.

3.3 Data collection

Data collection was carried out by contracting an external specialised panel: Andata research solutions. This procedure made it possible to guarantee the quality of the sample, as well as the segmentation of profiles and the traceability of the data collection process. In this way, a total sample of 700 observations was obtained, all from the Spanish territory, and segmented according to criteria such as gender, age or level of education, so that the results to be extracted can be conclusive and replicable.

3.4 Analysis techniques

Two main types of analysis were used. On the one hand, a theoretical analysis, to evaluate the specialised academic literature in the field of blockchain technology and tourism. Systematic reviews based on **PRISMA** guidelines and structured literature review approaches were used to integrate empirical evidence with a conceptual synthesis of the research field.

On the other hand, another part of the project has been developed through empirical analysis, for which two analysis techniques have been used: (1) **structural equation modelling**, and more specifically, PLS-SEM, since this is a technique with a causal explanatory and predictive approach whose fundamental strength is the estimation of complex models. Additionally, it is more suitable for exploratory research and theory development, and is more effective in small samples, as is the case in our research. And (2) **Chi-square Automatic Interaction Detection (CHAID)**, which is one of the most established algorithms within the family of hierarchical decision tree models. It is based on chi-square tests to detect significant associations between categorical or discretised variables, which makes it a particularly suitable tool for social and behavioural studies.

4. Scientific results and derived production

The development of the project has generated a relevant scientific production that has allowed the consolidation of a line of research focused on the analysis of the adoption of blockchain technologies and their impact on specific economic sectors, especially in the field of tourism and digital services.

During the project implementation period, several academic results have been produced, including scientific articles published or under review in international journals, book chapters in prestigious academic publishing houses and scientific dissemination activities at international congresses. . These results have contributed to positioning the research developed within the framework of current academic debates on digital transformation, technological adoption and governance of emerging technologies.

In particular, the project has led to the publication of a scientific article in the journal **Information Technology & Tourism**, focusing on the analysis of emerging risks and sustainability in the adoption of blockchain in the tourism sector. This work was based on a systematic review of the scientific literature and identified the main challenges associated with the implementation of this technology.

In addition, a book chapter has been published by **CRC Press (Routledge)** that has analysed the integration of blockchain technologies and biometrics in different strategic sectors, paying special attention to their implications in terms of security, digital identity and trust in digital environments.

In parallel, an additional chapter has been accepted for publication in the *Routledge **Handbook on AI and New Technologies in Tourism and Hospitality***, examining the role of blockchain in the transformation of business models in the tourism sector and in the generation of competitive advantages based on emerging technologies.

In addition to the results already published, the project has led to the development of several scientific articles that are currently under review in international journals. These works have focused on the empirical analysis of the factors that influence blockchain adoption by users and on the identification of differentiated adoption profiles using advanced statistical techniques. This work is currently at different stages of the review process in journals such as the **Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology** and the **Journal of Hospitality Management**.

In addition, the preliminary results of the project have been disseminated in the academic field through the presentation of a paper at the international congress **ACIEK 2025**, which has allowed obtaining scientific feedback and reinforcing the quality of the derived works.

In order to summarise the main scientific results generated during the project, Table 1 lists the publications and academic products associated with the project.

Table 1. Scientific production derived from the project

	Type	Title	Status	Media / Publisher
1	Scientific article	Managing Emerging Risks and Sustainability in Blockchain Adoption for Tourism Operations https://doi.org/10.1007/s40558-026-00366-2	Published 03/03/2026	Information Technology & Tourism
2	Scientific article	From Stimuli to Adoption: An S-O-R Approach to Blockchain Use in Tourism https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTT-10-2025-0851	Accepted. To be published 23/03/2026	Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology
3	Scientific paper	Beyond the Hype: Mapping Blockchain Adoption Profiles in Tourism Using CHAID	In 1st round of review 20/03/2026	Journal of Hospitality Management
4	Book Chapter	Integration of Blockchain and Biometrics: Applications, Benefits, and Challenges in Key Sectors https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003509554-10?urlappend=%3Futm_source%3Dresearchgate.net%26utm_medium%3Darticle	Published 05/10/2025	CRC Press (Routledge)
5	Book chapter	Blockchain-driven transformation in tourism: analysing competitive advantages and strategic implications for business models	Accepted. To be published 23/10/2025	Routledge Handbook on AI and New Technologies in Tourism and Hospitality
6	Conference paper	Building Trust Among Digital Generation: Strategies for Blockchain Adoption and Innovation	Presented 18-20 March 2025	ACIEK Conference 2025
7	Scientific paper	Improving the prediction of blockchain adoption for tourism operations by artificial neural networks	In preparation Pending journal submission April 2026	-

5. Sectoral applications of blockchain

The project has analysed the potential of blockchain technology in different economic sectors, with special attention to the tourism sector, considered one of the areas where the distributed registration technologies can generate significant transformations in management models, information systems and relations between the different actors in the tourism ecosystem.

The project has examined how the structural characteristics of blockchain - decentralisation, immutability of records, traceability of transactions and automation through smart contracts - can contribute to improving various processes linked to the provision of tourism services. In particular, the analysis carried out has shown that the technology can play a relevant role in reinforcing the security of digital transactions, reducing dependence on intermediaries and increasing transparency in the operations carried out between service providers and end users.

The study has also shown that blockchain can facilitate the development of more robust digital identity management systems. In tourism contexts, where the verification of user identity is essential for multiple processes -reservations, access to services, validation of transactions or loyalty programmes-, blockchain-based solutions have shown significant potential to improve the protection of personal data and increase user confidence in digital systems.

Another area where a relevant application potential has been identified is the traceability of information throughout the different stages of the tourism experience. The use of distributed records has made it possible to analyse the possibility of improving the traceability of transactions and services provided, which can help to increase the transparency of operations and reduce possible problems associated with the manipulation or loss of information.

Furthermore, the analysis carried out has highlighted that blockchain technology can facilitate new forms of coordination between the different actors involved in the tourism ecosystem, including service providers, digital platforms, public bodies and end users. In this sense, the decentralisation of information systems can favour the creation of cooperative environments based on shared digital infrastructures, where trust between parties is underpinned by verifiable technological mechanisms.

From a strategic perspective, the project has also identified opportunities for the development of new business models based on decentralised platforms and digital trust systems. In particular, it has been observed that the implementation of blockchain solutions can favour the emergence of alternative intermediation models, in which users and service providers interact more directly through digital infrastructures that reduce dependence on centralised platforms.

6. Economic and regulatory barriers

The analysis carried out in the framework of the project has identified various barriers that have conditioned the adoption of blockchain technology in different organisational contexts and sectoral contexts. In particular, it has been observed that the incorporation of this technology has been

limited by economic, institutional and regulatory factors that influence both the adoption decision by organisations and the perception of end users.

Among the main limitations detected have been the high costs of technological implementation, which include both the development of technical infrastructures and the adaptation of existing information systems and the training of specialised personnel. These initial costs have represented a significant obstacle for many organisations, especially in contexts where the potential benefits of the technology have not yet been perceived with sufficient clarity.

Furthermore, the analysis has revealed regulatory uncertainty surrounding the use of crypto-assets and distributed log-based technologies, which has led to caution on the part of companies and institutions interested in exploring their adoption. The absence of fully consolidated regulatory frameworks in certain areas has contributed to the perception of risk associated with the implementation of blockchain-based solutions.

Moreover, the perception of technological and operational risk has been identified as another relevant factor influencing the adoption of this technology. In particular, concerns related to platform security, data protection and the stability of certain digital ecosystems have affected the confidence of users and organisations.

These barriers have been analysed both from the perspective of the scientific literature and from the empirical results obtained during the development of the project, which has made it possible to identify common patterns in the factors that hinder the adoption of blockchain and to establish an analytical basis for future research aimed at overcoming these limitations.

7. Tax framework for cryptoassets and its relationship with the adoption of blockchain

During the development of the project, the tax context associated with the use of cryptoassets and the implementation of blockchain technologies has also been analysed.

The analysis carried out has shown that the economic and tax viability of blockchain adoption depends to a large extent on regulatory clarity and the reduction of legal uncertainty surrounding the taxation of cryptoassets. In the Spanish case, the tax treatment of these transactions has been based mainly on the application of general tax rules, especially in the area of personal income tax.

In general terms, transactions involving the transfer of virtual currencies by private individuals have been treated as capital gains or losses, calculated as the difference between the transfer value and the acquisition value. Likewise, certain transactions of exchange between crypto-assets have been interpreted as swaps that also generate tax effects.

In parallel, the Spanish tax system has incorporated a set of reporting obligations aimed at improving the tax control of transactions involving crypto-assets. These obligations are particularly aimed at platforms that hold or intermediate transactions with virtual currencies and at the declaration of assets located abroad.

At the European level, the development of specific regulatory frameworks for crypto-assets has helped to regulate the functioning of the market and improve the traceability of transactions. Although these regulatory frameworks have not been strictly tax-related in nature, their implementation has indirectly facilitated the fiscal control and supervision of transactions carried out in the blockchain ecosystem.

In this context, the analysis carried out has led to the conclusion that one of the main challenges for the tax system is to find an appropriate balance between ensuring tax compliance and promoting a regulatory environment that does not discourage the adoption of innovative technologies. In particular, the evidence suggests that intermediaries' information exchange mechanisms can play an important role in improving tax compliance without creating excessive regulatory burdens.

8. Financial implementation of the project

The budget initially requested for the project amounted to 1,585 euros, although funding of 1,250 euros was finally granted.

Most of the financial resources have been allocated to data collection through the contracting of an external specialised panel, which has allowed the empirical analysis of the project to be developed. Likewise, the remaining part of the budget has been allocated to scientific dissemination activities, including participation in international congresses (see table 1).

9. Conclusions

The project has made significant progress in understanding the factors that influence the adoption of blockchain technology from an interdisciplinary perspective.

The results obtained have shown that the adoption of this technology depends as much on psychological and social factors as on institutional and regulatory elements. In particular, variables such as trust, perceived security and institutional support have been shown to play a relevant role in the intention to use blockchain.

The research has also identified a number of economic and regulatory barriers that may limit its implementation, as well as laying the groundwork for future research aimed at developing economic-tax feasibility models applicable to different sectors.

10. Future projection and development of new research projects

The results obtained during the development of the project have made it possible to lay the foundations for the continuity of the line of research in competitive calls for proposals of greater scope, both nationally and internationally.

Firstly, the project has contributed to consolidating a conceptual and methodological framework that can serve as a basis for the development of new research proposals aimed at analysing the adoption of blockchain technologies in different organisational and sectoral contexts. In this sense,

the empirical evidence generated and the scientific production derived from the project have reinforced the viability of proposing larger-scale projects focused on the study of digital transformation in strategic economic sectors.

Likewise, the project has enabled the identification of new lines of research related to the economic-regulatory analysis of blockchain technologies, especially with regard to the development of economic-tax viability models and the study of the effects of regulation on the adoption of decentralised technologies.

In this context, the results obtained have facilitated the preparation of future research proposals that could be submitted to national competitive funding calls, as well as to international programmes aimed at the study of digital transformation and technological innovation.

On the other hand, the project has contributed to strengthening the international dimension of the research line through participation in academic conferences and the publication of papers in international scientific journals and magazines. This process has made it possible to expand scientific collaboration networks and establish contacts with researchers and research groups specialising in the analysis of emerging technologies.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the project has generated a solid base for the development of future research initiatives aimed at consolidating the internationalisation of the line of work, fostering scientific cooperation between institutions and promoting participation in international projects related to digital innovation and the adoption of blockchain technologies.